

On energy transfer of parametric resonance for wave energy conversion

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Abstract—Parametric resonance has been observed, both numerically and experimentally, in various studies of wave energy converters (WECs). A large motion in heave induces a periodic variation in the metacentric height of a WEC body, and, consequently, causes a harmonic variation in pitch/roll restoring coefficients, which can parametrically excite the pitch/roll modes. Current studies have a specific focus to determine the occurrence conditions of parametric resonance, by detecting the boundaries between stable and unstable regions in the parameter space. In the literature, some studies aim to make use of parametric resonance for improving power capture. In contrast, some studies try to suppress the effect of parametric resonance, as it reduces power capture efficiency. However, how energy transfers from one mode to another is not fully understood. This study aims to analyse the energy transfer between heave and pitch/roll modes when parametric resonance occurs. A generic cylindrical point absorber is studied as a WEC floater to considering non-linear wave-structure interaction, including non-linear Froude-Krylov and viscous forces. A heave-pitch-roll three-degree-of-freedom model is derived for numerical study of the energy transfer between different operation modes.

Index Terms—wave energy converter, parametric resonance, energy transfer, multiple degree of freedom, hydrodynamic modelling

I. INTRODUCTION

Parametric resonance is widely observed in engineering practice, which is viewed beneficial for the design of micro-electromechanical systems (MEMSs) [1] and energy harvesting systems [2], while it is treated as harmful phenomenon in ocean engineering, causing large undesired roll/pitch motion for ships and offshore platforms. For ships, the parametric resonance in roll motion is mainly due to the variation of the ship metacentric height induced by large heave motion, resulting in large roll motion, even capsizing. To suppress parametric resonance in ship rolling, a couple of passive and active control approaches, e.g. utilising fins or U-tanks, and manoeuvring cruise speed or yaw angle, are discussed in [3]. Spar-shaped offshore platforms are prone to parametric resonance, both in roll and pitch, mainly due to its large draft.

Parametric resonance has also been observed, both numerically and experimentally, in various studies of wave energy converters (WECs), e.g. oscillating water columns (OWCs) [4]–[7] and point absorbers (PAs) [8], [9]. A large motion in heave induces a periodic variation in the metacentric height of a WEC body, and, consequently, causes a dynamic variation in pitch/roll

restoring coefficients, which can parametrically excite the pitch/roll modes. Under certain conditions, e.g. the incident wave frequency equalling twice the pitch/roll natural frequency, parametric resonance occurs in pitch/roll modes and causes the pitch/roll motions to increase exponentially, known as Mathieu’s instability.

The onset conditions of parametric resonance for off-shore structure is more complex than that of Mathieu’s instability, as the hydrodynamics are highly non-linear and implicit. In addition, the occurrence of parametric resonance also significantly relies on the mass distribution [10], mooring design [11], [12], structure geometry [5], [13], [14], and hydrodynamic modelling methods [6], [9], [14]–[16].

Mathieu’s equation is generally used to explain the occurrence of parametric resonance, mainly assuming the heave motion is known or recorded [5], [10]. Thus the variation of the metacentric height is expressed as a function of heave and then parametrically excites the roll/pitch motions. However, experimental results indicates that the coupling between heave and roll/pitch is mutual [5], [15]–[17]. As the coupling between various degrees of freedom (DoFs) are highly non-linear, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) modelling in OpenFOAM is applied to depict heave-roll-pitch interaction for a truncated cylinder and a cylinder with a smooth hemispherical bottom in [14], which reveals the importance of viscous effect on parametric resonance. As expected, CFD modelling is expensive in computing. In addition, hybrid modelling methods, considering non-linear Froude-Krylov (FK) force with respect to instantaneous wetted surface, are utilised in a couple of studies [6], [16], [18].

Current studies have a specific focus to determine the occurrence conditions of parametric resonance, by detecting the boundaries between stable and unstable regions in the parameter space. However, there are only a few studies investigating the energy transfer from one mode to another. In the literature, some studies aim to make use of parametric resonance for improving power capture [4], [9]. In contrast, some studies try to suppress the effect of parametric resonance [5], [7], as it reduces power capture efficiency. For the Spar-Buoy OWC devices, parametric resonance is suppressed by passive fins [5] or actively controlled pressure relief valve [19]. However, how energy transfers from one mode to another is not fully understood.

This study aims to analyse the energy transfer between heave and roll/roll modes when parametric resonance occurs. The hybrid modelling method and corresponding open-access toolbox developed in [6], [18].

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Without loss of generality, a generic cylindrical point absorber is studied as a WEC floater to considering non-linear wave-structure interaction, including non-linear FK and viscous forces. A heave-roll-pitch 3-DoF model is derived for numerical study of parametric resonance, with specific foci on mutual interaction, viscous effect, multi-stability and energy transfer between different DoFs.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows: Section II discusses Mathieu's equation for modelling parametric resonance. Linear modelling method of the heave-roll-pitch 3-DoF PA is discussed in Section III, with the hybrid modelling method considering non-linear FK and viscous forces is described in Section IV. Numerical results are presented and discussed in Section V. Finally, Section VI draws some conclusions and indicated potential future work.

II. MATHIEU INSTABILITY

Mathieu's equation is widely used to explain onset and instability of parametric resonance. A good example is the Spar-Buoy OWC device, where parametric resonance in roll is observed numerically and experimental [5]. As Mathieu's equation to model parametric resonance is well described in [5], here only gives an overview as follows. For the heave-induced parametric resonance in roll, Mathieu's equation is given as

$$\frac{d^2\xi_4}{d\tau^2} + c\frac{d\xi_4}{d\tau} + [\delta + \epsilon \cos(\tau)]\xi_4 = 0, \quad (1)$$

where ξ_4 is the roll angle, and $\tau = \omega t$ is the time for Mathieu's equation. c , δ and ϵ are the damping, stiffness and amplitude constant parameters, given as

$$c = \frac{B_{44}}{\omega(M_{44} + A_{44})}, \quad (2)$$

$$\delta = \left(\frac{\omega_{n4}}{\omega}\right)^2, \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{|\hat{\xi}_3|}{GM_0} \left(\frac{\omega_{n4}}{\omega}\right)^2, \quad (4)$$

$$\omega_{n4} = \sqrt{\frac{\rho g V_d GM_0}{M_{44} + A_{44}}}, \quad (5)$$

where M_{44} , A_{44} , B_{44} , K_{44} are the inertia, added mass, radiation damping and hydrostatic stiffness in roll, respectively, depending on the hull geometry and wave frequency ω . ω_{n4} is the natural frequency in roll, as a function of the displaced volume V_d , average metacentric height GM_0 , and the total inertia $M_{44} + A_{44}$. ρ and g are the constant water density and gravitational acceleration, respectively. It is worthy to know that the amplitude of heave motion, $|\hat{\xi}_3|$, is assumed known.

As a classical differential equation, a systematic overview of Mathieu's equation is given in [20], with specific foci on its stability, non-linear extension, bifurcation and co-existence. The Mathieu-type instability in the $\delta - \epsilon$ parameter space is shown in Fig. 1, where δ and ϵ represent the frequency and amplitude conditions, respectively. For parameters in the unstable (or shadowed) region, the roll motion increases exponentially to infinity, called Mathieu instability.

Fig. 1. Instability chart of Mathieu's equation in Eq. (1), adopted from [20].

Though Mathieu's equation is useful to explain the onset of parametric resonance, there are some drawbacks for WEC modelling: (i) Mathieu's equation in Eq. (1) only considers a linear damping term and the roll motion increase exponentially to the infinity. In practice, a large roll motion induces some non-linear terms, e.g. quadratic or cubic damping term or stiffness, which can limit the maximum roll angle [20]–[22]. (ii) The motion in heave is assumed known or prescribed, and its information is needed in computing ϵ in Eq. (4). This is not always the case for WEC modelling. (iii) Mathieu's equation can only reflect the influence of heave motion on roll motion. However, this is partly true. The heave and roll motions are mutually coupled [15], and Mathieu's equation cannot express the influence of parametric resonance on heave mode.

This study utilises the hybrid modelling method to study the mutual interaction between heave, roll and pitch modes by considering non-linear FK forces, to investigate the quadratic viscous effect on parametric resonance by adding the Morison drag term to the linear model, and to discuss the influence of parametric resonance on WEC power absorption by applying passive control.

III. LINEAR MODELLING

As linear hydrodynamic modelling is the foundation of the hybrid modelling method, this section gives as overview of WEC linear hydrodynamics. A simple cylindrical PA is used in this study, with a radius of $R = 2$ m, a height of $H = 8$ m, a draft of $d = 6$ m, and a centre of gravity of $CoG = (0, 0, -3.1)$ m, as shown in Fig. 2. The water depth configured as $h = 100$ m.

For the cylindrical PA in Fig. 2, its dynamics is governed by Newton's 2nd Law, given as

$$M\ddot{\xi}(t) = \mathbf{f}_h(t) + \mathbf{f}_g(t) + \mathbf{f}_{pto}(t), \quad (6)$$

where M is the PA inertial matrix and ξ is the PA displacement matrix. \mathbf{f}_h , \mathbf{f}_g and \mathbf{f}_{pto} are the hydrodynamic, gravity and PTO (or control) forces, respectively. These parameters or variables contain heave, roll and pitch components, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The time t is omitted hereafter.

Fig. 2. Geometric of a cylindrical point absorber in heave-roll-pitch motion.

Based on linear potential flow theory, the hydrodynamic force \mathbf{f}_h can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{f}_h = \mathbf{f}_{fk,dy} + \mathbf{f}_{fk,hs} + \mathbf{f}_d + \mathbf{f}_r, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_{fk,dy}$ and $\mathbf{f}_{fk,st}$ represent the dynamic and static FK forces, respectively. \mathbf{f}_d and \mathbf{f}_r are the diffraction and radiation forces, respectively.

The summation of the dynamic FK force and the diffraction force is defined as the excitation force, given as

$$\mathbf{f}_e = \mathbf{f}_{fk,dy} + \mathbf{f}_d. \quad (8)$$

Meanwhile, the summation of the static FK force and the gravity force is called hydrostatic force, which is proportional to the PA displacement, given as

$$\mathbf{f}_{hs} = \mathbf{f}_{fk,hs} + \mathbf{f}_g = -\mathbf{K}\boldsymbol{\xi}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the hydrostatic stiffness. It is worth to mention that $\mathbf{f}_{fk,hs} + \mathbf{f}_g = 0$ holds when the body is at its equilibrium point in still water. The radiation force can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{f}_r = -\mathbf{A}_\infty \ddot{\boldsymbol{\xi}} - \mathbf{k}_r * \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}, \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{A}_∞ is the added mass at infinite frequency, and \mathbf{k}_r is the impulse response function (IRF) associated with the radiation force. $*$ is the convolution operator.

Substituting Eqs. (7)-(10) into Eq. (6), the WEC dynamics can be rewritten as Cummins' equation, given as

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\boldsymbol{\xi}} = \mathbf{f}_e + \mathbf{f}_r + \mathbf{f}_{hs} + \mathbf{f}_{pto}. \quad (11)$$

In the frequency-domain, Cummins' equation in Eq. (11) can be rewritten as

$$\{-\omega^2[\mathbf{M} + \mathbf{A}] + j\omega\mathbf{B} + \mathbf{K}\}\boldsymbol{\Xi}(\omega) = \mathbf{F}_e(\omega) + \mathbf{F}_{pto}(\omega), \quad (12)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Xi}(\omega)$ and $\mathbf{F}_e(\omega)$ are the frequency-domain representations of $\boldsymbol{\xi}(t)$ and $\mathbf{f}_e(t)$, respectively. $\mathbf{F}_{pto}(\omega)$ represents the control force. \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{K} are the added mass, radiation damping and hydrostatic stiffness, respectively.

To derive passive control method, Cummins' equation in Eq. (12) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\mathbf{V}(\omega)}{\mathbf{F}_e(\omega) + \mathbf{F}_{pto}(\omega)} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{Z}_i(\omega)}, \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{V}(\omega)$ represents the body velocity, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}(t)$, in the frequency domain. $\mathbf{Z}_i(\omega)$ is the intrinsic impedance of the system, given as

$$\mathbf{Z}_i(\omega) = \mathbf{B}(\omega) + j\omega \left[\mathbf{M} + \mathbf{A}(\omega) - \frac{\mathbf{K}}{\omega^2} \right]. \quad (14)$$

Thus, the passive control (PC) [23] can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{B}_{pto}(\omega) = |\mathbf{Z}_i(\omega)|, \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{B}_{pto} is the PTO damping coefficient for PC implementation. For a given wave frequency ω , the PTO force is given as

$$\mathbf{f}_{pto} = -\mathbf{B}_{pto}\dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}. \quad (16)$$

To quantify the power and energy captured from wave by the PA, the excitation power and energy are defined, respectively, as

$$\mathbf{P}_e = \mathbf{f}_e \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}, \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_e = \int_0^T \mathbf{P}_e dt, \quad (18)$$

where T is the integral time span. Similar, the absorbed power and energy by the PTO damper are defined, respectively, as

$$\mathbf{P}_{pto} = -\mathbf{f}_{pto}\dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}, \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_{pto} = \int_0^T \mathbf{P}_{pto} dt. \quad (20)$$

In this study, the boundary element methods (BEM) toolbox NEMOH is used, to obtain \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{A}_∞ , \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{k}_r directly. In Eq. 10, the convolution term, $\mathbf{k}_r * \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}$, is neither straightforward nor computationally efficient in WEC modelling and control. Thus, it is approximated by a finite-order state-space model using the time-domain methods in [24], [25], with the results show in Figs. 3(a)-(b). Alternatively, it can also be approximated by frequency-domain methods, as discussed in [26]–[28].

NEMOH can only give the frequency response function of the excitation force, $\mathbf{K}_e(\omega)$, and, thus, its IRF, $\mathbf{k}_e(t)$ can be computed according to

$$\mathbf{k}_e(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{K}_e(\omega) e^{j\omega t} d\omega. \quad (21)$$

Thus, the excitation force in the time domain can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{f}_e(t) = \mathbf{k}_e(t) * \boldsymbol{\eta}(t), \quad (22)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\eta}(t)$ is the incident wave. However, the excitation IRF is well-known as non-causal, shown in Figs. 4(a)-(b). The approximation of the convolution term, $\mathbf{k}_e(t) * \boldsymbol{\eta}(t)$ is not as straightforward as the radiation approximation. In the literature, a couple of methods are applied to approximate or estimate the excitation force [29]–[32]. In this study, the excitation

Fig. 3. Radiation approximation in (a) heave and (b) roll/pitch motions, respectively.

Fig. 4. Excitation approximation in (a) heave and (b) pitch motions, respectively.

Fig. 5. Comparison between the time- and frequency-domains liner models in terms of response amplitude operator (RAO) in (a) heave, and (b) pitch modes, respectively.

force approximation proposed in [30], [31] is adopted to derive a time domain model.

By approximating the radiation and excitation forces, a time-domain model for Cummins' equation is obtained, and its response amplitude operator (RAO) with various wave periods is compared with the frequency-domain counterpart in Fig. 5.

IV. NON-LINEAR MODELLING

To investigate the mutual interaction between multiple DoFs, the hybrid modelling method is used to compensate the linear Cummins' equation in Eq. (11)

with some critical non-linear forces. In this study, the non-linear FK force with respect to instantaneous wetted surface and the viscous force represented by the quadratic drag term in the Morison equation, are added to Eq. (11) as non-linear treatments, given as

$$M\ddot{\xi} = \mathbf{f}_{\text{nlfk,dy}} + \mathbf{f}_{\text{nlfk,st}} + \mathbf{f}_d + \mathbf{f}_r + \mathbf{f}_g + \mathbf{f}_{\text{pto}} + \mathbf{f}_v, \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_{\text{nlfk,dy}}$, $\mathbf{f}_{\text{nlfk,st}}$ and \mathbf{f}_v are the dynamic and static FK forces, and the viscous force, respectively. It is worth to note that the forces \mathbf{f}_d , \mathbf{f}_r , \mathbf{f}_g and \mathbf{f}_{pto} remain linear, as detailed in Section III.

The modelling of non-linear FK force is well studied in [18], [33], [34], and, thus, this paper only given an overview of its modelling described in [18], [33], [34]. For heave motion, the static and dynamic non-linear FK forces can be expressed as

$$f_{\text{nlfk,st},33} = \iint_{S(t)} p_{\text{st}} \mathbf{n} \, dS, \quad (24)$$

$$f_{\text{nlfk,dy},33} = \iint_{S(t)} p_{\text{dy}} \mathbf{n} \, dS, \quad (25)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the normal vector on the instantaneous wetted surface $S(t)$. The static and dynamics pressure components in the fluid are given as

$$p_{\text{st}} = -\rho g z, \quad (26)$$

$$p_{\text{dy}} = \rho g a \frac{\cosh(k(z+h))}{\cosh(kh)} \cos(\omega t - kx), \quad (27)$$

where a and k are the wave amplitude and wave number, respectively.

For the roll and pitch modes, the non-linear static and dynamic FK forces can be written as

$$f_{\text{nlfk,st},ii} = \iint_{S(t)} p_{\text{st}} (\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{n}) \, dS, \quad (28)$$

$$f_{\text{nlfk,dt},ii} = \iint_{S(t)} p_{\text{dy}} (\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{n}) \, dS, \quad (29)$$

where \mathbf{r} is the position vector of the instantaneous wetted surface to the CoG. The symbol \times represents the cross production. $ii = 44$ and $ii = 55$ represent the roll and pitch modes, respectively. Hence, the non-linear FK forces in heave, roll and pitch modes can be reshaped as

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{nlfk,st}} = [f_{\text{nlfk,st},33}, f_{\text{nlfk,st},44}, f_{\text{nlfk,st},55}]^T, \quad (30)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{nlfk,dy}} = [f_{\text{nlfk,dy},33}, f_{\text{nlfk,dy},44}, f_{\text{nlfk,dy},55}]^T. \quad (31)$$

In this non-linear hybrid modelling method, the concepts of ‘hydrostatic restoring force’ and ‘excitation force’ do not hold any more. However, their counterparts, the ‘non-linear hydrostatic restoring force’ and the ‘non-linear excitation force’ are defined for comparison, given as

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{hs,nl}} = \mathbf{f}_{\text{nlfk,st}} + \mathbf{f}_{\text{g}}, \quad (32)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{e,nl}} = \mathbf{f}_{\text{nlfk,dy}} + \mathbf{f}_{\text{d}}. \quad (33)$$

The viscosity effect of fluid on WEC dynamics is normally represented by a quadratic drag term according to the Morrison equation [35], given as

$$f_{\text{v},3} = -0.5\rho\pi R^2 C_{\text{d},3} \dot{\xi}_3 |\dot{\xi}_3|, \quad (34)$$

$$f_{\text{v},4} = -\rho R^4 d C_{\text{d},4} \dot{\xi}_4 |\dot{\xi}_4|, \quad (35)$$

$$f_{\text{v},5} = -\rho R^4 d C_{\text{d},5} \dot{\xi}_5 |\dot{\xi}_5|, \quad (36)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{v}} = [f_{\text{v},3}, f_{\text{v},4}, f_{\text{v},5}]^T, \quad (37)$$

where $f_{\text{v},3}$, $f_{\text{v},4}$ and $f_{\text{v},5}$ are the viscous forces in heave, roll, pitch, with viscous coefficient $C_{\text{d},3}$, $C_{\text{d},4} = C_{\text{d},5}$, respectively.

The values of $C_{\text{d},3}$, $C_{\text{d},4}$ and $C_{\text{d},5}$ are chose empirically, as discussed in [36], which depends on the Keulegan-Carpenter number, the Reynolds number and the roughness number. In practice, the viscous

coefficients can be determined analytically, numerically or experimentally [25], [37], [38]. However, it is difficult to obtain consistent values if wave conditions vary significantly [39]. In this study, the values in [15] are used, with $C_{\text{d},3} = 1$, $C_{\text{d},4} = C_{\text{d},5} = 0.7$.

To investigate the power and energy transferred from wave to the WEC, the non-linear excitation power and energy are defined, respectively, as

$$P_{\text{e,nl}} = \mathbf{f}_{\text{e,nl}} \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}, \quad (38)$$

$$E_{\text{e,nl}} = \int_0^T P_{\text{e,nl}} \, dt. \quad (39)$$

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the hybrid modelling method detailed in Section IV, numerical simulations are conducted to validate its capability to reveal the mutual interaction between multiple DoFs. An typical example is shown in Fig. 6, where the wave period is 6 s and the wave amplitude is 0.2 m. To focus on the mutual interaction problem, the viscous and PTO forces are not considered in Fig. 6.

For the initial conditions of $\xi_3(0) = 0$ m and $\xi_4(0) = 0$ rad, parametric resonance is not triggered. In Fig. 6, the heave and roll displacements by the non-linear model considering non-linear FK force (NLFK), to see the magenta curves, show no obvious differences from their linear counterparts (blue curves). For the initial conditions of $\xi_3(0) = 0$ m and $\xi_4(0) = 0.1$ rad, parametric resonance in roll occurs, and thus the roll angle is up to 1.2 rad, even though the wave amplitude is as small as 0.2 m. In turn, such a large roll motion results in a large heave motion, with maximum value about 2.5 m. Thus, the heave and roll modes are inherently and mutually coupled when parametric resonance occurs. Similar results are observed in [15], and thus, the hybrid modelling method with non-linear FK forces are capable to depict parametric resonance. In addition, the onset of parametric resonance is sensitive to initial condition, indicating the co-existence of multiple attractors. Such a multi-stability co-existence provides a possibility of supervision control, to switch between different attractors according to the sea states.

In Fig. 6, the heave and roll motions are unstable, which keep increasing as the simulation time increases. In practice, a large motion in heave, roll, or/and pitch induces significant non-linear hydrodynamics, and the viscous drag term should be considered. As shown in Fig. 7, both the parametric resonance in roll and pitch occurs for non-linear models, as the non-linear roll and pitch displacements are much larger than their linear counterparts. Comparing the black dashed curves with the magenta ones in Fig. 7(b), the viscous force attenuates roll motion significantly, while it only slightly damps the heave and pitch motions, as shown in Figs. 7(a) and (c), respectively. In Fig. 7, the wave period in 6.28 s, the wave amplitude is 0.1 m, and the PTO force is not included. Comparing Fig. 7 with Fig. 6 addresses the importance of viscous effect on prevent the motion increasing to infinity.

To discuss the influence of parametric resonance in WEC power/energy absorption, passive control with

Fig. 6. The effect of initial conditions on the occurrence of parametric resonance, illustrated by the heave and roll displacements in (a) and (b), respectively. In this figure, the PTO and viscous forces are not considered.

Fig. 7. Viscous effect on the parametric resonance in roll and heave, illustrated by the heave, roll and pitch displacements in (a), (b) and (c), respectively. In this figure, the PTO force is not included.

pure damper are implemented in the heave, roll and pitch modes in Fig. 8. The simulation conditions are wave period of 6 s and wave amplitude of 2 m. For the initial condition of $\xi(0) = [0, 0, 0]^T$, the parametric resonance is not set-on, while the parametric resonance occurs for the initial condition of $\xi(0) = [0, 0.1, 0]^T$.

The excitation energy in heave, roll and pitch modes are shown in Figs. 8(a)-(c), respectively, with their total in Fig. 8(d). Compared to the linear model, non-linear models always result less excitation energy in heave and pitch modes. It is very interesting that the excitation energy in roll is negative when parametric resonance occurs, as shown in Fig. 8(c), that is, the energy is dissipated. However, the heave, pitch and total excitation energy is insensitive to the occurrence of parametric resonance.

The absorbed energy by passive PTO dampers in heave, roll and pitch modes are shown in Figs. 8(e)-(g), respectively, with their summation in Fig. 8(d). Compared to the linear model, non-linear models result in much less PTO energy absorbed from heave and pitch, consequently a less total PTO energy. This is expected, as viscous forces can dissipate a lot energy. When parametric resonance occurs, it is possible to absorb some energy from roll, as shown in Fig. 8(f). Comparing Fig. 8(f) with Fig. 8(d), it is obvious that both the excitation energy and the PTO energy are null

when the parametric resonance is not triggered. After the onset of parametric resonance, the roll motion dissipates energy into wave, rather than harvests energy from wave. Thus, this part of energy can only come from the mutual interaction of roll mode with heave and pitch modes.

Although this study only reveals some preliminary insights into parametric resonance for wave energy conversion, some of findings are still debatable. (i) As shown in Figs. 6-8, the occurrence of parametric is sensitive to initial conditions, when there co-exist multiple attractors. Further study on the basin of attraction is required to check the stability of these co-existing attractors. This may also require a high-level supervision control system, to switch the system dynamics from one attractor to another, for triggering or suppressing parametric resonance. (ii) When parametric resonance occurs, the operation modes are coupled mutually. Improper modelling of such a mutual interaction may cause huge parametrically excited roll or pitch, as shown in Fig. 6, resulting in overoptimistic power absorption. In this case, proper modelling of non-linear hydrodynamics is critical, especially when parametric resonance is triggered, as demonstrated by Figs. 6-7. (iii) For WEC which can ideally and optimally harvest energy for all DoFs without any constraints, the power absorption approaches to its theoretical limits,

Fig. 8. Energy transfer between different DoFs illustrated by excitation energy in (a)-(d), and PTO energy in (e)-(h).

regardless of the occurrence of parametric resonance. However, most WEC devices are designed to harvest wave energy in one or two DoFs with stroke constraints. Pitching devices may make use of parametric resonance to absorb more power, as power in heave can be transferred to pitch. Alternatively, it is also possible for heaving devices to spill power to roll/pitch motion via parametric resonance, especially when the heave motion exceeds the stroke constraints. However, parametric resonance is characterised by high non-linearity, and its onset is sensitive to several factors, e.g. wave conditions, WEC hull geometry, mooring design, and control/PTO systems, more in-depth investigation is needed.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study uses a simple cylindrical point absorber in heave-roll-pitch modes to investigate the energy transfer between different DoFs when parametric resonance occurs. The hybrid modelling method, considering non-linear FK and viscous forces, can effectively and efficiently model the non-linear parametric resonance phenomenon.

Numerical simulation reveals that the heave, roll and pitch modes are mutually coupled when parametric resonance occurs, and improper modelling methods may lead to overoptimistic WEC motion and power absorption. The quadratic viscous terms can constrain WEC motions in some region, but also spill a lot of energy, resulting in much less power absorption than linear models. When parametric resonance happens, the roll mode cannot harvest energy from wave, but spill energy into wave, and thus this part of energy is transferred from the heave or/and pitch modes. However, the total excitation energy and PTO energy are insensitive to the onset of parametric resonance.

Ongoing work focuses on quantifying the energy transform from one DoF to another via parametric resonance.

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